

nitromethane in equilibrium with it. Pascal in his numerous investigations on the susceptibilities of organic compounds has not included many of the nitro compounds and still less the nitrates and the nitrites. The only nitro bodies investigated by him were nitrobenzene and nitrotoluene and the difference in this case for a CH_2 -group is -11.90×10^{-6} which when corrected for the new value of water, is reduced to -11.42×10^{-6} , a figure quite in proximity with our value of -11.36×10^{-6} .

Further work on the subject is in progress.

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Preparation of Compounds Related to Phenacetin.

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This work was undertaken with a view to prepare substances related to phenacetin (I) particularly those containing an acetyl group in the ethoxy side-chain. The following were prepared:—

(1) β -Hydroxy-*p*-nitrophenetole (II, R=H). (2) β -Acetoxy-*p*-nitrophenetole (II, R=Ac). (3) β -Benzoyloxy-*p*-nitrophenetole (II, R=Bz). (4) β -Salicyloxy-*p*-nitrophenetole (II, R=Salicyl). (5) β -Chloro-*p*-nitrophenetole (II, where Cl takes the place of OR in the side-chain). (6) β -Hydroxy-*p*-acetylaminophenetole (I, R=H). (7) β -Acetoxy-*p*-acetylaminophenetole (I, R=Ac). (8) β -Hydroxy-*o*-nitrophenetole (9) β -Acetoxy-*o*-nitrophenetole. (10) β -Benzoyloxy-*o*-nitrophenetole. (11) β -Hydroxy-*m*-nitrophenetole.

(I)

(II)

The compounds (6) and (7) were tested at the Haffkine Institute by courtesy of Father Caius S. J., but were found to have no antipyretic action. Preliminary attempts to reduce the nitro compounds to amino compounds were unsuccessful. The compounds prepared are now described as there is no immediate possibility of continuing this work.

EXPERIMENTAL.

β -Hydroxy-p-nitrophenetole.—Sodium nitrophenate (120 g.), ethylene chlorhydrin (60 g.) and 50% alcohol (150 c. c.) were heated at 120° for 23 hours. The upper oily layer was treated with ether which separated the required product (29 g.) in nearly pure form; a further yield (20 g.) was obtained from the ether extract. The water layer, on concentration, gave a small yield (8 g.). The product is soluble in almost all organic solvents and also moderately in water. It crystallises from benzene in long transparent needles, m. p. 101.2°. (Found : N, 8.1. $C_8H_9O_4N$ requires N, 7.6 per cent).

With acetyl chloride-pyridine the above product gave *β -acetoxy-p-nitrophenetole* which crystallises from carbon tetrachloride in transparent rectangular plates, m. p. 85-87°. (Found : N, 6.4. $C_{10}H_{11}O_5N$ requires N, 6.2 per cent).

β -Benzoyloxy-p-nitrophenetole crystallises from dilute methyl alcohol in clusters of thin transparent plates, m. p. 116°. (Found : N, 5.2. $C_{15}H_{13}O_5N$ requires N, 4.9 per cent).

β -Salicyloxy-p-nitrophenetole.— *β -Hydroxy-p-nitrophenetole* and salicyl chloride in molecular proportions were kept in a desiccator for 2 days and the resulting mixture was heated at 100° under reduced pressure (water pump) for some hours to remove salicyl chloride. The mixture was extracted with benzene and the residue after evaporation of benzene, was crystallised from carbon tetrachloride, m. p. 133°. (Found : N, 4.67. $C_{15}H_{13}O_6N$ requires N, 4.62 per cent).

β -Chloro-p-nitrophenetole.— *β -Hydroxy-p-nitrophenetole* was heated with phosphorus pentachloride (1 mol.) at 100° until evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased. The product was mixed with powdered ice, the solid separating, crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in long, thin needles, m. p. 67-68°. (Found : N 7.3. $C_8H_8O_3NCl$ requires N, 7.0 per cent).

β-Hydroxy-p-acetylamino-phenetole.—*p*-Acetylamino-phenol (27 g.), ethylene chlorhydrin (15 g.) and 2*N*-NaOH solution (7.5 g.) were heated at 60-70° for 8 hours, the oil separating (27 g.) solidified when kept at 0°. It crystallised from acetone-benzene in transparent plates, m. p. 116-17°. (Found: N, 7.6. C₁₀H₁₃O₃N requires N, 7.2 per cent). With acetic anhydride-H₂SO₄ it gave *β-acetoxy-p-acetylamino-phenetole* which crystallised from benzene in shining plates, m. p. 130°. (Found: N, 6.3. C₁₂H₁₅O₄N requires N, 5.9 per cent).

β-Hydroxy-o-nitrophenetole.—A mixture of sodium-*o*-nitrophenate (30 g.), ethylene chlorhydrin (15 g.), and water (10 c. c.) was heated at 125° for 20 hours and extracted with ether. The extract was washed with caustic soda solution and water and after drying it was distilled under reduced pressure, b. p. 180°-182°/4 mm., yield 44 g. (Found: N, 7.4. C₈H₉O₄N requires N, 7.6 per cent). The compound gives *β-acetoxy-o-nitrophenetole* with acetyl chloride-pyridine, b. p. 201°-202°/4 mm. (Found: N, 6.4. C₁₀H₁₁O₅N requires N, 6.2 per cent).

β-Benzoyloxy-o-nitrophenetole crystallises from dilute acetic acid in clusters of transparent plates, m. p. 75-76°. (Found: N, 4.8. C₁₃H₁₃O₅N requires N, 4.9 per cent).

β-Hydroxy-m-nitrophenetole.—A mixture of *m*-nitrophenol (2.5 g.) in 40% KOH solution (1 g.) and ethylene chlorhydrin was heated at 100° for 2 hours. The product crystallised from acetone-petroleum ether, m. p. 90-91°, yield 2 g. (Found: N, 7.8. C₈H₉O₄N requires N, 7.6 per cent).